

Collisions Free Scheduling in the NEPHELE Hybrid Electrical/Optical Datacenter Interconnect

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Abstract— The NEPHELE datacenter network is divided into pods/clusters of racks and relies on hybrid electro-optical top-of-rack switches that access an all-optical network consisting of WDM rings. To enable dynamic and efficient sharing of the optical resources and a collision-free network operation, the NEPHELE network is envisioned to be operated in a slotted TDMA manner with a software-defined-network (SDN) based control plane. We describe the NEPHELE resource allocation problem, describe the wavelength conflicts on the shared WDM rings, translate those into resource allocation constraints and discuss on the effect of these constraints on the network performance. To do so, we define the worst-case traffic and perform simulations to evaluate their effect on average traffic. Finally, we propose a variation to the NEPHELE architecture that reduces the effects of these wavelength conflict constraints.

Keywords—slotted operation; time division multiplexing (TDM); wavelength division multiplexing (WDM); rings; resource allocation; scheduling; wavelength collisions;

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread availability of cloud applications, as well as the emergence of platform- and infrastructure-as-a-service models, have been enabled by the existence of centralized computing infrastructures, typically referred to as Data Centers (DCs). DCs are comprised of a large number of servers running Virtual Machines (VMs) that are grouped into communicating racks. The performance of a DC is determined, not only by its computing capacity but also by the capabilities and performance of its interconnection network infrastructure. Given the trend, it becomes apparent that incoming and local traffic within the DC will continue to increase in the following years [1]. As a result, interconnection aspects of DCs will play a crucial role in their further development, and thus, high throughput, scalable and energy/cost efficient network architectures are required to fully harness the DC potential.

Currently, the state-of-the-art networks in DCs are based on electronic switching in fat-tree topologies [2]. The fat-tree approach tends to underutilize resources, requires a high cable count, suffers from poor scalability and finally is not energy efficient [3]-[4]. Storage is typically accessed over a separate network and implemented following Fibre Channel protocol. Current trends include the disaggregation of computing, storage, and memory resources, the convergence of data and storage networks and application driven networking that seem problematic under the current architecture solutions. To cope with the shortcomings of fat-tree networks, hybrid interconnects consisting of an optical circuit switching and an electrical packet switching network have been proposed. There are many recent works, such as [3], proposing such alternate

DC architectures in which the heavy and long-lived traffic is selectively routed over the circuit switched network, while the rest goes through the packet switched network. However, the classification of traffic is quite difficult while it has also been observed that long-lived and heavy flows are not typical and a high connectivity degree is needed [4].

To enable dynamic and efficient sharing of the optical resources and a collision-free network operation, the NEPHELE architecture was proposed, introducing the concept of a slotted optical DC interconnect. In the NEPHELE network “slots” are time segments that can be accessed for rack-to-rack communication following the time division multiplexing (TDM) concept. “Slots” (and therefore network resources) can be assigned dynamically to communicating racks, and the NEPHELE approach can attain high utilization of the network capacity, leading to both energy and cost savings. Traffic is forwarded over multiple fiber rings that utilize multiple wavelengths, that is, they utilize wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) as a means of increasing the capacity. In particular, the NEPHELE network consists of independent planes, each employing several fiber rings. A ring and a slot is used for a *transparent* connection between two racks. In this TDM and WDM environment, slots need to be assigned so as to avoid the wavelength conflicts within the rings.

In this paper we describe the NEPHELE DC network architecture, the resource allocation problem and focus on the constraints coming from that architecture. We formally describe the wavelength conflicts within the shared WDM rings, translate those into resource allocation constraints and discuss on their effect on the network performance. To do so, we define the worst-case traffic and perform simulations to evaluate their effect on average traffic. Finally, we propose a variation to the NEPHELE architecture that reduces the effects of these wavelength conflict constraints.

II. THE NEPHELE INTERCONNECT

NEPHELE is a hybrid electrical/optical Data Center (DC) interconnect architecture, built out of the pod switch, the NEPHELE top-of-rack (TOR) switch and the NEPHELE network interface controller (NIC) subsystems. The NEPHELE network consists of P pods (clusters) of servers. A pod is a collection of W racks, each consisting of Z servers; a rack is accessed through its respective TOR switch. The TORs inside a pod and between the pods are interconnected through I parallel and identical *planes*, each of which consists of R unidirectional rings connecting the P pods. Each fiber ring carries WDM traffic comprising W wavelengths, propagating simultaneously in the same direction (unidirectional). So, a pod consists of W TOR switches and I POD switches that are interconnected in

the following way: each TOR switch has I northbound ports, each facing one of the I POD switches. A wavelength addresses a specific TOR inside a pod (the number of wavelengths W equals the number of TORs in a pod), while wavelengths are reused among the pods. The TOR switch is a hybrid electrical/optical switch: the electrical part of the TOR is connected “south” to ZL_e server ports with “conventional” Ethernet links and to ZL_o optical server ports and “north” to other TOR switches through the I planes of the all-optical NEPHELE pod network. Fig. 1a briefly describes the NEPHELE interconnect.

As it has already been mentioned, NEPHELE operates in a slotted TDMA manner, resembling the operation of a single (but huge) TDMA switch with the ports of the TOR being the input/output ports of the switch (IPW ports). The NEPHELE maintains the (time)slot component of TDMA, but slots are no longer statically assigned to circuits (TOR-to-TOR communications). Rather, slots are dynamically assigned by a central scheduler based on the respective traffic requirements. However, taking scheduling decisions in a per-slot basis seems to be prohibitive, due to communication and processing latency limitations. Thus, it seems to be more efficient to do the resource allocation periodically so that scheduling decisions are

taken for periods or cycles of T lots; this way enables the aggregation and suppression of monitoring and control information and also absorbs traffic peaks, reducing the dynamicity of the resource allocation process.

We now explain how communication is performed in the NEPHELE network assuming a slot as the switched entity (Fig. 1b). The traffic of a slot originating from a TOR enters a POD switch and is first switched through a fast 1×2 space switch according to locality; if the traffic is destined to a TOR inside the same pod it remains within the POD switch, otherwise it is routed to the rings and to the next POD switch. Local intra-pod traffic, after the 1×2 switch, enters a $1 \times W$ arrayed waveguide grating (AWG) where it is passively routed, depending on the wavelength of the incoming signal and the input port. For a generic $N \times M$ cyclic (CAWG) the static routing function that gives the output port is

$$out_port = (in_port + w) \% M,$$

where $0 \leq in_port \leq N$ is the input port, $0 \leq w \leq W$ the used wavelength, and “%” denotes the modulo operation. Inter-pod traffic is routed via the fast 1×2 switch towards a second $W \times R$ CAWG followed by couplers that combine multiple CAWG outputs into the fiber rings. So, the traffic enters the ring according to the CAWG function, propagates in the same ring through intermediate POD switches and is dropped at the destination pod. These routing decisions are applied by setting appropriately the related wavelength selective switches (WSS) in the POD switches. The WSSs can select whether a slot is passed or dropped on a per-fiber, per-wavelength and per-slot basis. So each intermediate POD sets the related WSS to the pass state, while at the destination the related WSS is set to drop. The drop ports of the WSSs - corresponding to all the rings - are introduced into a $I \times W$ AWG and are passively routed to the W TORs in that pod. Through this AWG the traffic reaches the specific destination TOR.

III. NEPHELE DYNAMIC BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION

NEPHELE aims to provide network resources in a dynamic and re-configurable fashion. To this end, TOR switches periodically report their bandwidth requests to the network controller, or applications report their requirements to the controller. The controller constructs a $WP \times WP$ traffic matrix (TM) at the end of each reporting period. Each traffic matrix entry $TM(w_1, p_1, w_2, p_2)$ corresponds to the number of timeslots that have been requested for the communication between a source TOR(w_1, p_1) with a destination TOR(w_2, p_2), where p_1 and p_2 indicate the source and destination pods and w_1 and w_2 indicate the wavelength/position of the source and destination TORs inside the related pods, $1 \leq w_1, w_2 \leq W$ and $1 \leq p_1, p_2 \leq P$. This communication, however, must be performed in a coordinated manner to avoid collisions between transmissions inside the optical network. Let us denote an indicative communication as $[TOR(w_1, p_1) \rightarrow TOR(w_2, p_2), i, t]$, assuming that transmission takes place over plane $1 \leq i \leq I$ at timeslot $1 \leq t \leq T$. The following scheduling constraints (SC) must then be enforced:

- SC1. No other communication $[TOR(w_3, p_3) \rightarrow TOR(w_2, p_2), i, t]$, for all $1 \leq w_3 \leq W$, $1 \leq p_3 \leq P$ on this slot t and plane i . This constraint ensures that the reception of the transmission is performed in a collision-free manner at TOR(w_2, p_2).
- SC2. No other communication $[TOR(w_1, p_1) \rightarrow TOR(w_3, p_3), i, t]$, for all $1 \leq w_3 \leq W$, $1 \leq p_3 \leq P$ on this slot t and plane i . This constraint describes the fact that the TOR(w_1, p_1) cannot

Fig. 1 (a) The NEPHELE architecture, (b) the NEPHELE POD switch

transmit to multiple destinations simultaneously in the space (plane) and time (timeslot) domains.

SC3. No communication $[\text{TOR}(w_3, p_3) \rightarrow \text{TOR}(w_2, p_4), i, t]$, for all $p_1 < p_3 < p_2$ or $p_1 < p_4 < p_2$, and $w_3 = w_1 + kR$, with k integer so $1 \leq w_3 \leq W$, in the same slot t and plane i . This constraint ensures that no transmission that starts or ends at an intermediate pod and is forwarded to the same ring will appear within the same fiber ring (output of the CAWG).

The coordination of transmissions is achieved by expressing the TM as a sum of binary matrices, called *permutation matrices* (PM) that conform to all three constraints. Each PM represents the configuration of the network for a single slot and a single plane. Constraints 1 and 2 can be enforced in a straightforward manner by allowing a single ‘1’ per column and row, respectively, on the PM. The third constraint mandates that a single ‘1’ will exist on the corresponding permutation matrix positions.

Note that in the above analysis, planes are identical and the scheduling conflicts are independent of the plane. Following this, slots and planes are treated homogeneously as a single type of resource to be allocated. The solution is written as IT permutations, and there is no distinction how these permutations are split into the related slots – plane resources.

The above bandwidth allocation problem becomes a TM decomposition problem into IT permutations that can be optimally solved using the Birkhoff–von Neumann theorem [5] and bi-partite graph matching [6]. Given the high execution time of optimal decomposition, we have explored a heuristic scheduling algorithm which examines sequentially each TM entry and allocates an equal number of ‘1’ in PMs by sequentially searching them to find those that all three scheduling constraints are met. This algorithm exhibits improved execution time at the expense of underutilizing slots and planes, but this only manifests at relatively high network loads. Accounting for the typical (first two) scheduling constraints SC1 and SC2 is done in linear time, using data structures of size $ITPW$. Accounting for SC3 is done in superlinear time, using a data structure of size ITP^2W to keep track of the sub-rings that are defined by the source-destination pods of the connections (enabling the re-use of the remainder sub-ring by other connections). To reduce the running time we have considered a variation of SC3, referred to as *full-ring SC3*, where a communication is assumed to conflict over the whole ring not the particular source-destination pod sub-ring (reducing to linear the size of the related data structure).

A. Worst case traffic

We now discuss about the worst case traffic pattern for the NEPHELE network that is built with I identical planes that have the above described scheduling constraints. The worst case traffic pattern assumes that all $Z(L_O + L_E)$ ‘south’ ports of $\text{TOR}(w_1, p)$, $1 \leq p \leq P/2$, communicate with the respective ‘south’ ports located in $\text{TOR}(w_2, P-p+1)$, and this traffic is bidirectional, meaning that we also have $\text{TOR}(w_2, P-p+1) \rightarrow \text{TOR}(w_1, p)$ communication. All such communicating pairs, due to their specific TOR source and destination addresses, if routed on the same plane would result in the same ring using the same wavelength, that is, they are conflicting regarding scheduling constraint SC3. Assuming that a single server from each TOR communicates with a single destination server, there are $P/2$ connections conflicting ($(P+1)/2$ if P is odd).

Thus, $P/2$ planes are required for all such communication. Since there are $Z \cdot (L_E + L_O)$ servers/end ports in every rack, the total number of required planes is: $I = Z \cdot (L_E + L_O) P/2$.

B. NEPHELE Architecture Variation

To reduce the number of planes required for the worst case traffic we proposed a variation of the reference NEPHELE architecture that employs non-homogeneous planes with different transfer functions. We assume that the drop AWG function of plane i , $1 \leq i \leq I$, and pod p , $1 \leq p \leq P$, is described by a constant $f(i, p) = c$, $0 \leq c \leq W-1$, which is different for different planes and pods ($f=0$ for all planes and pods in the baseline NEPHELE architecture). Following this assumption a rack in a pod is no longer addressed with a specific wavelength, but the wavelength to reach that depends on the destination pod and the plane. To be more specific, assume again the communication $\text{TOR}(w_1, p_1) \rightarrow \text{TOR}(w_2, p_2)$ on plane i . Assume that we use wavelength w at the source so that ring $r = (w_1 + w) \% R$ is used and $w_2 = (w + f(i, p_2)) \% W$ is satisfied to reach the specific destination. Now, take a conflicting pair $\text{TOR}(w_3, p_3) \rightarrow \text{TOR}(w_4, p_4)$. In order for a pair to be conflicting, the same wavelength w and the same ring should be used, so $r = (w_3 + w) \% R$ and also p_3 or p_4 should be in between p_1 and p_2 . Thus, again $w_3 = w_1 + kR$ and $p_1 < p_3 < p_2$ or $p_1 < p_4 < p_2$ need to hold as in SC3. To reach the destination rack w_4 the following should hold: $w_4 = (w + f(i, p_4)) \% W$. So in this case we do not need to have $w_4 = w_2$ as was the case in SC3, but we need $w_4 - w_2 = f(i, p_4) - f(i, p_2)$. Our goal is to avoid this conflicting pair to conflict in any other plane. So we want to satisfy $f(i, p_4) - f(i, p_2) \neq f(i', p_4) - f(i', p_2)$, for all $1 \leq i' < I$, $i' \neq i$. To be more general, we want the above to hold for any conflicting pair of any plane, that is for all p_1, p_2 ($p_2 \neq p_1$), p_3, p_4 ($p_4 \neq p_3$), w_1, w_2 , and $i < I$.

For odd R we can construct a solution to this problem with the following recursive rules:

$$f(i, 1) = 1, \text{ for all planes } i, 1 \leq i \leq I,$$

$$f(i, p) = [f(i, p-1) + i - 1] \% R + 1, 1 \leq i \leq I, 2 \leq p \leq P.$$

For even R , such construction is not feasible, but we can assume that we use $R+1$ rings and follow the above construction (the extra cost for high R is minimum). Following these rules, the number of planes I required to serve any pattern is then $I = Z \cdot (L_E + L_O)$. To see this, assume that all traffic is conflicting in a plane (as was the worst case traffic for baseline NEPHELE architecture describe above). There are $I-1$ planes that this traffic is not conflicting, and assuming $P/2 \leq I-1$, this traffic can be served by these planes. So, the number of planes required for worst case traffic and thus the number of ‘northbound’ TOR ports equals the ‘southbound’ TOR ports (to servers), typical for conventional TOR switches.

In this architecture variation, the wavelength used to reach each destination changes per plane. So, we need to have a map (can be pre-calculated) that would assign a wavelength to each combination of destination TOR per plane. This action is actually a table lookup that takes sublinear time. Also, the transfer function of each plane is different, and thus, the planes are no longer equal and are not allocated the same as the slot resources. So, we need for each plane to pre-calculate the conflicting pairs and avoid those in the T slots that correspond to that plane. In this sense, the scheduling constraint SC3 is translated to a plane assignment constraint. We can again have two variations, in the context of keeping

track and examining the conflicts either in sub-rings or in full-rings; these are referred to as the *plane-variation/sub-ring* and *plane-variation/full-ring* SC3, which require super-linear or linear time, respectively.

IV. PERFORMANCE RESULTS

We evaluate the performance of the NEPHELE architecture and the proposed variation via simulations for parameters: $I=P=20$ and $W=T=80$, which correspond to a fully-fledged NEPHELE implementation. The TMs were generated periodically (every T timeslots) with the adjustable traffic load and variation between successive TMs. In particular, the traffic generator initially created a TM with identical row and column sums by randomly activating connections (TM entries). Each entry was taken to be equal to a parameter GI , which also reflects the sparsity of the TM: high sparsity (GI) values corresponded to the existence of traffic hotspots, since the number of non-zero TM entries equals $\rho IT/GI$, where ρ denotes the network load. Given an existing TM instance, the generator would create a new one, by randomly modifying the former by a selected percentage (dynamicity=0.1%, 1% or 10% - only 1% shown here due to space limitations) of the active connections, in order to take into account the impact of the temporal traffic dynamicity; these connections have their traffic reduced by GI , while others (active or inactive) have their traffic increased by the same amount, so that the total load was constant among periods and equal to $\rho ITWP$.

We assessed the performance using the developed heuristic decomposition algorithm for: (i) the reference architecture/sub-ring SC3, (ii) the reference architecture/full-ring SC3, (iii) plane variation/sub-ring SC3 and (iv) plane variation/full-ring SC3. Note that in all examined cases the number of planes was the same. Cases (i) and (ii) have worst-case TM that require more ($P/2 = 10$ times) planes, while cases (iii) and (iv) have enough planes to serve any traffic. The probability of generating the worst-case TM is extremely low, but cases (i) and (ii) have several TM instances that would require more than I planes, while for cases (iii)-(iv) there are no such instances. Note, however, that we use a heuristic and thus blocking is expected even for cases (iii)-(iv).

Table 1 shows the maximum throughput defined as the maximum load that the network can support. To find this, the non-served traffic of a period was added to the next period and we observed at which load (depending on the architecture case) traffic started to accumulate infinitely, typically referred to as unstable operation. We can observe that the performance of the reference architecture both considering sub-ring and full-ring (case (i) and (ii)) exhibit low throughput as the network becomes sparser, that is, as GI increases. The reason is that sparse TMs result in the emergence of hotspots, and the bigger the hotspots are, the bigger the problem becomes, if they are conflicting in terms of the SC3. This is added to the fact that sparser TMs are more difficult to be served by the heuristic, which explains the small decrease of the throughput for the plane variation architecture cases (iii) and (iv) as GI increase. As expected, the performance of the sub-ring cases (i) and (iii) are better than the related full-ring cases (ii) and (iv). However, if we examine the execution time (shown in

Fig. 2 only for $GI=40$), we can observe that the higher throughput comes at a higher algorithm execution time. So we observe a tradeoff between the performance and the execution time. Note that the execution time of the scheduling algorithm for the plane variation architecture is slightly higher than the execution times for the reference architecture, due to the additional considerations of the wavelength table lookup and the specific plane allocation.

TABLE I. MAXIMUM THROUGHPUT FOR MEDIUM DYNAMICITY (1%)

GI	reference architecture/ sub-ring SC3	reference architecture/ full-ring SC3	plane variation/ sub-ring SC3	plane variation/ full-ring SC3
4	0.8	0.7	0.9	0.9
40	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.8
200	0.3	0.2	0.8	0.7

Fig. 2. Average execution time as a function of load for medium dynamicity (1%) and semi-sparse traffic ($GI=40$).

V. CONCLUSIONS

The NEPHELE interconnect is based on slotted TDMA operation to enable the dynamic and efficient sharing of the optical resources and collision-free operation. We described the NEPHELE resource allocation problem and focused on the architecture specific constraints. Wavelength conflicts on the shared WDM rings are translated into resource allocation constraints that affect the network performance. We described the worst-case traffic and performed simulations to evaluate their effect on average traffic. We proposed a NEPHELE architecture variation that reduces the effects of the wavelength conflict constraints, with very low overhead.

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